

COOLSCHOOLS

NATURE-BASED CLIMATE ACTION FROM SCHOOLS TO CITIES

2022-2025

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May 2025, Barcelona

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The COOLSCHOOLS Research Project

Coolschools (March 2022-Feb. 2025, <http://coolschools.eu>) is an applied-research project aiming to analyze the multiple co-benefits of implementing nature-based solutions (NbS) for climate adaptation in school environments. We have explored how these nature-based climate school shelters can act as drivers of transformation at larger urban scales through an inter- and transdisciplinary approach that puts the focus on the needs and views of children and youth.

The project builds and expands on the experience of four pioneer European projects in the implementation of NBS for climate change adaptation in school environments (primary and secondary education)

Brussels Ose le vert (2016-2023), Opération Ré-création (2021-2024)

Barcelona Climate Shelters in schools (2018-2021), Transformem els patis (2021-onwards)

Paris Oasis (2018-onwards)

Rotterdam Groenblauwe schoolpleinen (2019-onwards)

Our conceptual framework proposes and advances nature-based climate shelters as innovative strategies for urban climate adaptation focusing on school environments. It goes beyond the idea of locally confined, safe cooling centers with air conditioning; instead, our approach leverages the multiple co-benefits of nature-based solutions (NbS) in order to achieve enhanced community health and well-being.

We have studied the different capacities and impacts resulting from the implementation of nature-based climate shelters in school environments from the perspectives of social justice, biodiversity conservation, public health, safety, inclusive governance and quality education from schools to the metropolitan region.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003758 (Next-GenerationEU"/PRTR) and the Spanish Research Agency (PCI2022-132958; MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033), Innoviris (Brussels Capital Region), Dutch Research Council (NWO), The Research Foundation—Flanders (FWO), and Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR).

Barcelona

Paris

Brussels

Rotterdam

WPI Accessibility inequalities

- 93 % of primary schools in Brussels, Barcelona, Paris and Rotterdam have less than 30% green and blue infrastructure (GBI) cover within a 300m buffer.
- In Brussels, children from wealthier families significantly benefit from greener and healthier outdoor school environments, including greener schoolyards.
- Based on an urban region-wide survey, 40.5 % of schoolchildren in Brussels visit a public green space nearby their school after school hours, and one-third (33%) visit these public green spaces at least several times per month.
- Schoolchildren from disadvantaged families in Brussels tend to use public green spaces after school hours more frequently than children from higher income families.

Objectives

- To assess the outdoor environmental quality of primary schools in Brussels using a multi-indicator distributive justice approach, taking into consideration access to different urban GBI elements, provision of regulating ecosystem services, and exposure to environmental hazards.
- To assess the spatial patterns of GBI in and around school environments and their changes over time across four large European cities – Brussels, Barcelona, Rotterdam, and Paris – from an equity perspective.
- To explore children's use patterns of green spaces during and after school hours in Brussels and understand the main enablers and barriers to children's use of green spaces

Methodology

GIS-based spatial analyses were performed to map and assess GBI elements, regulating ecosystem services, and environmental hazards in 408 primary school environments located in the Brussels Capital Region. These were then related to the socio-economic characteristics of schools to uncover potential environmental (in)justice implications. Similarly, we measured exposure to GBI around all primary schools in Brussels, Barcelona, Rotterdam and Paris using European Copernicus Urban Atlas data from 2006 and 2018. Through bivariate, spatial regression and cluster analyses, we analysed the relationships between environmental indicators and schools' socio-economic background. Finally, using a Public Participation GIS (PPGIS) tool, we disseminated two map-based surveys to parents/guardians and school staff to understand the (unequal) use patterns of public green spaces by children aged 3-12 during and after school hours.

List of Publications

- Gallez, E., Mujica, C. P. F., Gadeyne, S., Canters, F., & Baró, F. (2024). **Nature-based school environments for all children? comparing exposure to school-related green and blue infrastructure in four European cities**. *Ecological Indicators*, 166, 112374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.112374>
- Gallez, E., Canters, F., Gadeyne, S., & Baró, F. (2024). **A multi-indicator distributive justice approach to assess school-related green infrastructure benefits in Brussels**. *Ecosystem Services*, 70, 101677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2024.101677>
- Phillips, A., Gallez, E., Canters, F., Gadeyne, S., & Baró, F. (in preparation) **Characterizing children's use of public green spaces after school hours using participatory GIS**.
- Gallez, E., Gadeyne, S., Canters, F., & Baró, F. (in preparation) **Barriers and Opportunities for Children's Use of School-related green spaces in Brussels: Insights from School Staff** (in preparation).
- Gallez, E., Phillips, A., & Baró, F. (2025). **Children's use of green spaces during and after school hours in Brussels - VUB survey results** (REPORT). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14938078>

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Main Results

In the Brussels-Capital Region, children from wealthier families significantly benefit from greener, healthier and more climate resilient school environments. Similarly, when comparing school types, we find that private schools tend to be greener compared to public and charter schools (Fig.1). No significant differences were found between schools from the French- and Dutch-speaking educational systems. These results reveal strong school-related socio-environmental inequities in Brussels.

Figure 1: Schools' outdoor environmental quality indicators stratified by school type, in the Brussels Capital Region.

When compared to Brussels, Barcelona, Rotterdam and Paris, Brussels is the urban area with the most prominent school-related socio-environmental inequities (Fig.2). In Brussels and Rotterdam, affluent children tend to benefit from greater exposure and access to GBI. The opposite is found in Paris, and to lesser extent, in Barcelona. In the four cities, most primary schools (93%) have less than 30% GBI cover within a 300m buffer. We did not find substantial gains or losses in school-related GBI in the assessed period (2006-2018).

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of primary schools' clusters in Brussels, Barcelona, Rotterdam, and Paris

The Brussels region-wide survey on children's use of public green spaces (PGS) after school hours revealed that disadvantaged children tend to visit public green spaces (PGS) more often than wealthier families. While PGS located nearby school are visited by nearly half (40.5%) of all schoolchildren once or more per month, they tend to be smaller and less vegetated than those visited further away from schools. Pre-school-aged children (3-6 years old) use PGS significantly more frequently than primary school-aged children (6-12 years old). The main enabling factors perceived by parents who regularly visit PGS is the proximity to safe and accessible (by public transport, bicycle, or on foot) PGS close to school and/or home (Fig.3)

Figure 3: Enablers and barriers to use of PGS by frequent users (i.e., those visiting once or more per month) (n = 271).

Most schools (76%) organize short nature-based outdoor activities (lasting less than 1 day), at least once every 2-3 months outside school premises. However, in schools with a majority of children from lower-income families, teachers and children tend to travel longer distances to reach green spaces for these activities. Time constraints, staff shortages, and limited support from pro-environmental organizations are the barriers most frequently mentioned by school staff to organizing nature-based activities. Conversely, school proximity to green spaces, staff motivation and experience, and school curriculum requirements are seen as important enabling factors.

Conclusions

Urban inequities in children's access and exposure to school-related GBI benefits revealed in the four cities studied in this research - Brussels, Barcelona, Rotterdam and Paris -, demonstrate the need for urban planners and policymakers to prioritize greening policies in school environments (e.g., transformation of schoolyards) with a focus on schools with a majority of disadvantaged pupils. Improving safety, quality and maintenance of GBI within and around school settings should be a priority for decision-makers. Our research demonstrates that PGS visited nearby schools tend to be smaller and less vegetated than other PGS. Hence, increasing vegetation in PGS visited nearby schools should be prioritized, particularly considering it is children from the least wealthy families who make the most of use PGS during the weekday. Finally, education authorities should increase school resources (time availability, staff, external supports, etc.) to promote the organization of outdoor activities during school hours, so children have equal opportunities to enjoy the multiple benefits of nature.

WP2 Biodiversity practices

- Schoolyard revegetation fosters biodiversity and human-nature interactions in cities.
- Effective nature-based solutions require governance shifts, cultural adaptation, and community effort.
- Green schoolyards enhance biodiversity and inspire life-focused teaching practices

Objectives

WP2 aimed to study how greening schoolyards, initially designed for climate adaptation, also supports broader Nature-based solutions (NbS) goals, including urban biodiversity, social-ecological transformation, and human-nature relationships. The research hypothesizes that revegetating schoolyards drives administrative changes, supports a diverse range of spontaneous flora and fauna, enhances ecological networks, and encourages interactions between users and nature. Three questions guided the study: How does the socio-technical production of NbS in schoolyards take place? What is the ecological contribution of vegetated schoolyards? How can schoolyards become observatories of human-nature interactions?

Methodology

We proposed a mixed, multidisciplinary methodological approach that explores both the ecological dimensions of biodiversity, and the representations and practices of stakeholders invested in a schoolyard transformation program. The contribution of schools to biodiversity was assessed by arthropod inventories carried out in schools and nearby green spaces, as well as by ecological network modelling to assess functional connectivity. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted with stakeholders involved in the design, implementation and/or management phases of schoolyard renaturation. By combining species inventories with semi-structured interviews, we aim to connect the quantitative and qualitative dimensions of NbS

Figure 1: Number of arthropod morphospecies collected in schoolyards and the nearest green spaces in Paris. Source: Mélanie Gippet

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Main Results

Modalities of the socio-technical production of nature in school grounds

The Paris schoolyard greening project involves diverse stakeholders but faces communication and staffing challenges, impacting governance and management. Despite initial oversight of biodiversity, a 2020 shift emphasized vegetation inspired by Brussels' approach, prioritizing ecological and cost-effective solutions. Schoolyards now integrate permeable materials and greenery, improving biodiversity and promoting children's well-being, a key argument for stakeholder support. However, management clarity, staff expertise, and resource availability remain issues, with two-thirds of schools unclear on support roles. Biodiversity efforts focus on aesthetic and safe plant choices, constrained by space, pupil density, and reliance on local species, limiting ecological potential.

Schoolyards are home to a diverse range of spontaneous wildlife

Arthropod abundance and diversity were assessed using data collected in 26 green schools (16 in Paris, 5 in Brussels, 5 in Barcelona) and 16 nearby green spaces (Paris). Results show that schoolyards host diverse and abundant arthropod communities, sometimes in numbers comparable to those found in green spaces (figure 1). The arthropod communities present in schools and green spaces differ in their composition by more than 70%, probably due to the differences in vegetation composition.

Perceptions and representations

Fieldwork focused on three OASIS-qualified Parisian elementary schools, in different arrondissements, with the agreement of the teaching and after-school staff (Picpus school, Paris 12, with 238 pupils surveyed), (Pontoise school, Paris 5, with 66 pupils surveyed), (Bruxelles school, Paris 9, with 140 pupils surveyed). In terms of methodology, data collection was aimed at analyzing the representations of nature held by playground users - children, teachers and extracurricular organizers - through qualitative interviews (50) and the production of drawings, based on the instruction to "draw nature in your playground" (without a model or direct visual access to the object drawn) (900 drawings).

Conclusions

The successful transformation of schoolyards using NbS depends on management by biodiversity experts and the long-term commitment of the educational community, including school staff, pupils, parents and municipal services. These vegetated schoolyards could pave the way for new teaching practices more focused on interactions with living organisms.

Schoolyards in Paris, Brussels, and Barcelona host diverse and abundant arthropod communities, comparable to those in urban parks, although their composition is substantially distinct, probably due to vegetation and management differences.

More vegetation and better connections between green areas help increase the number of birds and pollinators in the four cities. So, greening schoolyards represents a valuable opportunity to enhance urban biodiversity and help to stop its decline.

Challenges remain in green schoolyards' management and educators' expertise and resources to develop innovative teaching approaches that support biodiversity.

List of Publications

- Blanc Nathalie, Celine Clauzel, Cedissia About, Anne-Laure Riché, Mélanie Gippet, Sarah Bortolamiol. **Schoolyards greening for connecting people and nature: an example of nature-based solutions?** People and Nature (under Review)
- Clauzel Céline, Louis-Lucas Tanguy, Blanc Nathalie, Bouteau François, Bortolamiol Sarah, Clavel Joanne, Grésillon Etienne, Laurenti Patrick. **Schoolyard greening to improve functional connectivity in the city and support biodiversity.** Urban Forestry and Urban Greening (under review).
- Louis-Lucas Tanguy, Clauzel Céline, Blanc Nathalie, Bortolamiol Sarah, Clavel Joanne, Grésillon Etienne. **Where should we green our cities? Exploring Landscape Connectivity's impact on Urban Biodiversity.** Biological conservation (under review).
- Philippot Véronique, Clauzel Céline, Blanc Nathalie. **Un jardin secret apprenant qui ni se dessine ni se dit sans attention : la cour d'école à l'épreuve de l'enquête et l'inventaire.** Recherches en éducation. (under review).
- Clauzel, C. et al. 2023. **Colloquium on the role of educational spaces in urban biodiversity. COOLS-SCHOOLS.** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13908371>
- Philippot, V. 2025. **Operational guide for educational initiatives related to biodiversity practices in nature-based schoolyards aimed at school staff: from research to the learning field. COOLSCHOOLS.** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14966404>

WP3 Children's development

- We investigate the associations between exposure to green spaces and cognitive performance, behavior and well-being of 339 children in the 5th and 6th grade of 22 elementary schools in Brussels.
- Preliminary descriptives show that total behavioral problems are more prevalent in less green schools.
- These differences vary depending on the type of behavioral problem and the socio-economic background of the school.
- First results show a consistent protective effect of school green spaces on total difficulties and hyperactivity or inattention symptoms. This result was more pronounced for the presence of trees in schools with a high proportion of deprived children.

Objectives

The objective of work package 3 (WP3) was to investigate the associations of school yard and surrounding green spaces with cognitive function and well-being of pupils aged 10 to 12 years and attending the 5th or 6th grades of primary schools in the Brussels Capital Region

Methodology

We selected schools in 4 groups: 1) low socioeconomic (SE) background and low greenness, 2) high SE background and low greenness, 3) low SE background and high greenness, and 4) high SE background and high greenness. Pupils in the 5th and 6th grade were invited to participate. Percentage of tree canopy and vegetation cover was assessed for each school (schoolyard and within a buffer of 300m) and home address (within a buffer of 300m). Outcomes measured were cognitive performance (neuropsychological tests), behavior (strengths and difficulties questionnaire) and general health related well-being (KIDSCREEN-27 questionnaire)

List of Publications

- Bentouhami, H., et al. 2024. **School and pupil participation in the health impact assessment for work package 3. COOLSCHOOLS.** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13908424>
- Bentouhami, H., et al. 2025. **Nature-based climate school shelters and behavioural development. COOLSCHOOLS.** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15011573>
- Bentouhami, H., Croons, H., Berden D., Gallez, E., Baró, F., Nawrot, T., Casas, L. **School green spaces and childhood behavioural problems: findings from the COOLSCHOOLS study.** Environmental Research (under review)

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Main Results

In total, 22 primary schools consented to participate and 339 pupils were included. The mean age of the pupils was 11 years (9.56-13.36 years), and half were female. About 70% of the pupils had at least one parent who completed higher education (college or university), and both parents employed.

To date, the analyses regarding the health and well-being outcomes have focused on the behavioral problems, and are still ongoing. Here, we present preliminary results for behavioral problems that should be interpreted with caution. Overall, 10% of the pupils scored positive for behavioral problems (total difficulties). By type of behavioral problem, most prevalent problems were hyperactivity or inattention (14.5%) followed by emotional problems (13.9%). The least prevalent were peer relationship problems (6.5%). Figure 1 shows the prevalence of behavioral problems by category of school greenness and SE background. The proportion of pupils with total difficulties was lowest in high green schools (9.7%, n = 18). By school SE background, the total difficulties prevalence difference between low and high green schools was slightly bigger for low SE background schools as compared to high SE background schools. A similar pattern is observed for emotional problems. Peer relationship and hyperactivity/inattention problems were less prevalent in high green schools, but only in low SE background schools. Contrarily, conduct problems in low SE background schools were more prevalent when the school green was high, while in high SE background schools the prevalence was lower in high green schools. These associations were weak and warrant further investigation.

Results of the adjusted analysis show a protective (non-significant) effect of school green spaces on behavioral problems. After stratification for the SE background of the school, it seems that there is significant protective effect of school vegetation (trees) for hyperactivity/inattention symptoms in schools with a high proportion of deprived children (figure 2).

Figure 1: prevalence (%) of pupils with suspected behavioral problems per category of school.

Figure 2: Adjusted associations for the relationship between behavioral problems and school tree canopy cover by SE background of the school; *adjusted for sex, age and parental education, including school as random effect.

Conclusions

This work package investigates the relationship of schoolyard and school surrounding green spaces with cognitive performance, behavior and well-being of children attending primary schools in Brussels. So far, the statistical analyses are ongoing. Preliminary descriptions of behavioral problems indicate that their prevalence is higher in schools with less green schoolyard and surrounding green spaces, with bigger differences observed in schools of low SE background. Nevertheless, the observed differences vary depending on the type of behavioral problem and the socio-economic background of the school. These results must be interpreted with caution as they do not consider the impact of potential confounders.

WP4 Socio-Cultural perceptions

- WP4 investigated how perceived quality characteristics of school climate shelters, in particular those related to safety, determine the capacity of green and blue schoolyards to initiate socio-cultural transformations in the neighborhoods. In order to do so, WP4 employed the innovative method of Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping (FCM), which was further developed to be suitable for research with children.
- Over half of Rotterdam's schoolyards feature a wide range of greenery. Design and play elements, such as natural surfaces and natural sitting spaces, are common. Water features and wildlife habitats appear less often, potentially due to safety concerns.
- We find that children, teachers, and parents perceive safety related to greenery differently. For children, greenery, cleanliness, and the presence of other people boost the sense of safety—among those factors, cleanliness matters most. School staff see greenery as increasing and parents as decreasing safety. These findings highlight the need to balance safety and inclusivity in schoolyard design

Objectives

WP4 explored how perceived quality and safety of school climate shelters influence the ability of nature-based solutions (NbS) to drive socio-cultural change. Its goals were to:

- (1) Review current knowledge on the link between perceived safety and urban NbS;
- (2) Assess the physical features of Rotterdam's current, 35 Blue and Green schoolyards;
- (3) Examine how schoolyard elements shape safety and quality perceptions among children, teachers, and parents to evaluate their role as climate shelters and drivers of socio-cultural transformations in the neighborhood.

Main Results

Perceived Safety in Nature-Based Solutions (NbS)

The literature review identifies several physical factors affecting perceived safety in urban green spaces, such as maintenance, vegetation, design, and the presence of others. People feel safer in legible, well-maintained areas that offer visibility and freedom of movement, while wild or unclear spaces can evoke vulnerability. Safety perceptions vary by age—children and older adults often feel less safe—and by gender, with women reporting greater unease in these environments

List of Publications

Paper Submission, Urban Forestry & Urban Greening journal - Nature-based solutions and safety concerns – A systematic review to foster urban transitions, May 2024
 Poster Presentation, ECIU Conference, Barcelona – Spain, October 2023 “Resilient communities in schoolyards, the example of Rotterdam”
 Poster Presentation, Climate Day – University of Twente, Enschede – The Netherlands, November 2024 “Creating Climate Shelter in Rotterdam schoolyards”

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Methodology

WP4 used three main methods: (1) A systematic review aided by machine learning to explore links between safety perception and NbS; (2) The Green Schoolyard Evaluation Tool to assess physical features of schoolyards in Rotterdam; (3) Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping to explore views on quality and safety in green schoolyards

Insights from Green Schoolyard Evaluation Tool (GSET) in Rotterdam

The GSET assessment of 35 of Rotterdam's Green and Blue schoolyards revealed that greenery was present in most spaces, with over half containing all green-related elements listed in the tool. Among the five GSET categories—greenery, design, playing and learning, water, and habitat for animals—the least represented categories were water elements and animal habitats, present in only 17 schoolyards. These may suggest an influence on safety

Table 1: GSET results – Greenery in 35 schoolyards (Source: Authors)

Children's and Adults' Perception of Safety in Green Schoolyards in Rotterdam

FCM was employed to analyse the perceived cause-effect relations between schoolyard quality and safety among children, school staff, and parents (Fig. 1). One of the advantages of FCM is its ability to facilitate scenario analysis. In this case, key factors such as greenery, the presence of other users, and maintenance were examined. For children, all three factors—greenery, maintenance, and the presence of other users—positively influence their perception of schoolyard safety. However, aspects related to maintenance, such as reduced garbage, less graffiti, improved upkeep, and overall cleanliness, have the most substantial impact on their safety perception (Fig. 2). School staff associate increased greenery with a heightened perception of safety, whereas parents perceive an increase in greenery as diminishing safety

Table 2: GSET results – Water in 35 schoolyards (Source: Authors)

Figure 01: Network of safety and quality perception of children about their schoolyard (Source: Authors)

Figure 02: Scenarios. Increasing Greenery, Maintenance and Presence of other users for the three user groups (children, school staff and parents). (Source: Authors)

Conclusions

This research identified key factors that shape safety and quality perceptions of school climate shelters and may thereby drive socio-cultural transformations by way of NbS in urban areas. We find that perceived safety mainly depends on maintenance, vegetation type, design features, and the presence of others. On schoolyards, in Rotterdam, water elements and animal habitats also invoke safety concerns. The analysis also showed that children, school staff and parents perceive greenery differently: children responded positively to greenery, maintenance, and user presence—with cleanliness and upkeep having the strongest impact on safety. School staff linked greenery to greater safety, but parents saw it as reducing safety. These findings stress that effective NbS planning must account for maintenance and the balancing of ecological goals with safety concerns

WP5 Governance arrangements

- Effective and vigorous schoolyard governance rests on the extent to which the nature-based interventions are integrated into, or even transform, existing pedagogical philosophies and practices.
- The quality of stakeholders' engagement, is fundamental from a justice and inclusion perspective.
- Dedicating sufficient time for green schoolyards' design and development may strengthen their inclusivity and adaptability.
- Ambitious programs around nature-based schoolyards require that central institutional actors align well around the initially set of transformational goals.
- A "catalogue approach" to schoolyards transformation might be useful from efficiency considerations, but if designed on the basis of squarely technical, financial and security-related considerations it might bar diversity, creativity and eventual participation.

Objectives

In this thread of work, we explored the key factors that underpin the effective, just, and lasting nature-based transformation of schoolyards. This often means looking at the very configurations that enable and sustain the manifold benefits of green schoolyards. To this aim, we explored the way green schoolyards are initiated, negotiated and further envisioned, by whom and with what implications, paying particular attention not only to the effectiveness of reaching set goals, but to questions of justice, equity and reflexivity in the process of co-creation. In particular, we analysed the norms, actors, processes and competences through which school playgrounds are conceptualized, designed, implemented, sustained and used.

List of Publications

- Sekulova, F., Calvet Mir, L., Ruiz-Mallen, I. Stakeholder entanglements around making schoolyards greener and climate adaptive. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, (in press).
- Corres, A. G., Ruiz-Mallen, I., Sekulova, F. What learning outcomes result from co-creating nature-based schoolyards? An analysis of sustainability competences, in "Disruptive Initiatives in Education for Climate Emergency" eds. Conde, J. García-Vinuesa, A. Ángel Meira, P. C. Springer. (in press)
- Ruiz-Mallén, I., Marlès, J., Mestre, A., Baró, F., Sekulova, F. (2024). El potencial transformador de los refugios climáticos escolares basados en la naturaleza. (pp. 999- 1010). Libro de actas del XXII Coloquio de Geografía Urbana /I Coloquio Internacional de Geografía Urbana. AGE Valladolid – Burgos
- Sekulova, F., Ruiz-Mallen, I. 2024. The governance configurations of greening schoolyards. *Environmental Science and Policy*. Volume 156, 103752
- Ruiz-Mallén, I., Artero Borrue, M., Sekulova, F. (2024). Pathways towards nature-based climate shelters in school environments. Special workshop "Green Oasis for the 15 minutes city model". Proceedings of the 14 Biennale of European Towns and Town Planners, Naples. Edited by Marichela Sepe. INU Edizioni.
- Sekulova, F., Colacios, R., Ruiz-Mallén, I. (2024). Video on the collaborative process of envisioning the paths to more inclusive nature-based climate school shelters' co-management
- Ruiz-Mallén, I., Baró, F., Satorras, M., Atun, F., Blanc, N., Bortolamiol, S., Casas, L., Clauzel, C., Colacios, Sekulova, F. (2023). Refugios climáticos escolares basados en la naturaleza: evaluación desde una perspectiva interdisciplinaria. *Papers. Regió Metropolitana de Barcelona*, 65, 61-76.
- Ruiz-Mallén, I., Baró, F., Satorras, M., Atun, F., Blanc, N., Bortolamiol, S., et al. Sekulova, F. 2023. Nature-Based Solutions for Climate Adaptation in School Environments: An Interdisciplinary Assessment Framework, in *Sustainable Urban Transitions: Research, Policy and Practice*, Allam, Z. editor, Springer Nature The good governance of nature-based schoolyards (from Sekulova and Ruiz-Mallén, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103752>)

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Methodology

- 1) Academic and grey literature analysis on green schoolyards, comprising texts published in indexed journals, supplemented by reports by public institutions and relevant non-for-profit organizations.
- 2) 53 semi-structured interviews among representatives of school communities, public administration officials, and architects (n=30 for Barcelona, n=23 for Brussels); 3 additional interviews with public officials and non-governmental organizations working in the field of naturalizing schoolyards from Paris and Rotterdam.
- 3) One year of field work observation and participative research around schoolyard transformation at two schools in Barcelona, including participatory future scenario workshops with children and adults (2023-24).
- 4) Social-network analysis (11 responses for Barcelona, and 10 for Brussels)

Main Results

Nature-rich and diverse schoolgrounds do not automatically result in educational, social and cognitive attainments, unless accompanied by adults/teachers. The literature is unequivocal that without the active teacher engagement and promoting their training on sustainability competences green schoolyards can hardly attain their full potential. Children are frequently considered non-experts and excluded from consultations on the later stages of development. The tokenistic involvement of children obstructs their full appreciation of, and care for, the new nature-rich space.

Rushed time-frames may impede the continuous feedback of children, parents, and teachers to inform the final schoolyard designs and lead to disappointing results. Dedicating sufficient time for green schoolyards' design and development may strengthen their inclusivity and adaptability.

Ambitious programs around nature-based schoolyards require that central institutional actors align well around the initially set transformational goals, so that the resources, funds and time invested are best harnessed. In the case of Barcelona, the standard institutional practice of cementing schoolyards is being slowly and successfully subverted by progressive municipal policies. In Brussels, creativity, authenticity and thinking out of the box around climate adaptation, nature access, and diversifying play, are stimulated by granting more agency to actors with a background in grassroots participation, environmental and nature-based education, landscape ecology.

Tensions have been recorded in those schools where teachers and children had a versatile vision of the schoolyard, or demanded less paved and more vegetated, creative, multifunctional and free play-oriented space than mainstream designs guided by a "catalogue approach". Many of those quarrels have been successfully navigated whenever school communities were adamant about de-pavement and landscape-oriented design, yet when they had the power to influence the architectural approach. The transformation that occurred is a manifestation of the capacity and/or power of school communities to produce their environments.

As the social-network analysis indicates the direct communication channels between schools in our sample were still to be established. Strengthening the horizontal links across schools could potentially facilitate the sharing of experience and know-how around maintenance, but also for institutionalizing a response to the challenges of managing a space that requires more hands-on approaches.

The good governance of nature-based schoolyards (from Sekulova and Ruiz-Mallén, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103752>)

Conclusions

From a just and responsive governance perspective, the quality of the stakeholder engagement processes, either as an element of planning, or as a type of iterative and transformative participation is an achievement on its own. Good schoolyard governance entails pulling synergies together, while understanding, and embracing differences in perspectives, needs, and responsibilities, and addressing dynamics of power and representation.

The more schoolyards get transformed, naturalized, diversified and used as educational spaces, the stronger the influence, or pressure, on educational institutions to abandon the logic of the barren and homogeneous playgrounds. Diversifying schoolyards, may eventually diversify schools.

Cross-school communication is fundamental for pollinizing ideas around greening schoolyards over time and space. Green schoolyards can only unfurl their multiple benefits when the 'mentality of care' for the commons gets installed within the community, particularly among teachers.

WP6 Educational transformations

- Good practices and learnings on the transformation capacities of nature-based climate shelters in schools
- Capacity-building activities for teachers
- Outreach to Ministries of Education (MoEs)
- Generating knowledge and tools

Objectives

Guiding European schools to become nature-based climate shelters based on evidence from other COOLSCHOOLS focus areas, and helping students, teachers, and others understand the core steps and constraints in the process.

Training teachers on using nature-based climate shelter interventions for educational purposes and helping them introduce their co-benefits to their students by engaging them in the implementation of climate shelters in schools.

Disseminating best practices on nature-based climate shelters.

Producing recommendations for MoEs to ensure COOLSCHOOLS' outputs are taken up by those developing school STE(A)M education strategies, and by other urban climate adaptation decision-makers.

Methodology

COOLSCHOOLS' educational transformations target teachers, Heads of schools, school administration and Ministries of Education. Research, based on the activities of the four research cities, supports the preparation of guidelines for schools with the core steps to start the process of becoming a nature-based climate shelter. A Massive Online Open Course helps educators introduce nature-based climate shelters interventions in schools for educational purposes, and encourages them to create their own action plans, as well as exchange best practices through a targeted campaign. A recommendations-based policy brief, informed by COOLSCHOOLS' work in research and education, is provided for the Ministries of Education.

List of Publications

- Grand-Meyer, E., et al. 2024. COOLSCHOOLS Guidelines for schools with the core steps to start the process of becoming a climate shelter. COOLSCHOOLS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14966950>
- Tezas, N. et al. 2024. Nature-based climate shelters in Schools: Empowering Teachers for Sustainable Education. MOOC (2024) Report. COOLSCHOOLS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001771>
- Grand-Meyer, E., et al. 2024. Policy brief on the COOLSCHOOLS recommendations for Ministries of Education to achieve a school's transition towards climate shelters. COOLSCHOOLS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14966968>
- EUN. 2024. Nature-based Climate Shelters in Schools. <https://www.europeanschoolnetacademy.eu/courses/course-v1-COOLSCHOOLS+GreenSchools+2024/about>

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Main Results

COOLSCHOOLS MOOC: "Nature-Based Climate Shelters in Schools: Empowering Teachers for Sustainable Education" (2024). / <https://zenodo.org/records/14001772>

The MOOC, in collaboration with Scientix® – the community for science education in Europe, presented the concepts of Nature-based climate shelters in schools and Urban nature-based solutions (NBS) through design thinking. Nature-based climate shelters in schools are green spaces in schoolyards accessible to both students and the broader community that help mitigate the impacts of climate change, while offering a space for outdoor learning. Through Nature-based climate shelter interventions (CSIs), educators learned to engage students in the design of a nature-based climate shelter in their own school to allow them to develop agency in improving their surroundings, 21st century skills and environmental awareness. The MOOC took place from 1 April to 8 May 2024. It was free and open to anyone, targeting teachers with all levels of experience from all subject areas. The MOOC remains accessible in an archived format on the European Schoolnet Academy platform, and a report on the MOOC is available on the Scientix website.

Campaign promoting best practice and climate shelters action plans

The Campaign, organised in the Autumn of 2024, involved dissemination via social media and various online channels to promote best practice and climate shelters action plans among teachers in Europe. The Campaign also included the webinar series "Greener Schools for Greener Minds" in collaboration with Scientix®, inspired by the MOOC's Action plan template and design-thinking approach elements

The COOLSCHOOLS Guidelines for Schools: how to turn your schoolyard into a nature-based climate shelter / <https://zenodo.org/records/14966951>

These Guidelines help School leaders, teachers, and community members such as parents, understand the practical steps and considerations to plan and design schoolyard transformations into nature-based climate shelters to obtain a range of benefits for health, learning, social cohesion, and biodiversity. The advice provided is based on the experience of four case-study cities (Barcelona, Brussels, Paris, Rotterdam), where municipalities have undertaken the transformation of a large number of schoolyards as part of their climate resilience strategy

Analysis of steps needed and constraints for developing the Guidelines

An analysis of the steps needed and constraints for developing the Guidelines for schools on the core steps of designing a nature-based climate shelter, was prepared.

Policy brief on the COOLSCHOOLS recommendations for MoEs to achieve a school's transition towards climate shelters / <https://zenodo.org/records/14966969>

A policy brief will be produced to ensure that decision-makers and those interested in formulating or influencing education, environment, and urban policy are coherently informed about the benefits and challenges when navigating towards nature-based climate shelters in schools.

Conclusions

COOLSCHOOLS's work on educational transformations focuses on: 1) leveraging COOLSCHOOLS' growing body of policy insights, good practices and learnings on the transformation capacities of nature-based climate shelters, and 2) promoting teachers' capacity building and outreach activities to Ministries of Education across Europe, so that even more schools and European regions could benefit from and use the knowledge and education tools generated by COOLSCHOOLS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101003758

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. [number]

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